

ON THE PROCESS OF DEVELOPING MIRZACHOL

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Anattation: The issues and problems of development of protected and gray lands in the field of agriculture in Uzbekistan in 1946-70 and the provision of these areas with qualified personnel are covered.

Keywords: Communism, dissatisfaction, party, guard, religion, atheism, cadres, obsolescence, press, desert, resource, enlightenment, creed, national, mentality, assimilation, migration.

Резюме. 1946 – 70 йилларда Ўзбекистонда қишлоқ хўжалиги соҳасида амалга оширилган кўриқ ва бўз ерларнинг ўзлаштирилиши ва бу худудларни мутухассис кадрлар билан таъминлаш масалалари ва муаммолари ёритилган.

Калит сўзлар: Коммунистик, кўнимсизлик, партия, кўриқ, дин, атеизм, кадрлар, эскилик сарқити, матбуоат, чўл,ресурс, оқартув, ақида, миллий, менталитет, ўзлаштириш, кўчиш.

During the Soviet era of command-based management, in Uzbekistan, as in all colonies, extensive methods of production were widely used, regardless of the objective laws tested for the socio-economic development of society. In particular, the special resolution of the Central Committee of the CPSU and the Council of Ministers of the USSR "On measures to develop cotton growing in the Uzbek SSR" adopted on February 2, 1946 set the task to increase cotton production in Uzbekistan 2.5 times in 4-4 years. Based on this decision, the resettlement of people to the newly developed lands, including Mirzachul, has been accelerated [1]. To this end, from the second half of the 1940s, more attention was paid to the "voluntary-compulsory" relocation of the population from the provinces to Mirzachul. The people of Uzbekistan, who worked selflessly on the front and behind the war, were tasked with developing new lands for the further development of cotton growing. A number of measures have been taken to improve the socio-economic situation of the displaced population, new settlements have been built, and migrants have been provided with housing. However, due to the complex climatic conditions of Mirzachul and the lack of demand for hastily built housing without taking into account the mentality of the local population, social problems have escalated and staff shortages have not been eliminated.

In the last years of the USSR government, along with national conflicts throughout the union, the escalation of socio-economic crises did not bypass the population of Mirzachul. We still remember with sadness that the people of Jizzakh

were slandered and blamed during the Soviet era by the former Center for the "cotton affair", "the affair of the Uzbeks", "rashidovism", and all this fell on the shoulders of ordinary, innocent people. Especially the people of Jizzakh, who were heartbroken by such injustice, but did not bow to him, were slandered in the face of various slanders against the humble and wise statesman, well-known writer SharofRashidov, who ruled Uzbekistan in very difficult and difficult years. "It's worth bowing to his endurance and perseverance" [2].

The issue of population migration is a complex process, and since ancient times, humanity has been trying to move from one area to another in search of a comfortable place to improve its habitat and living conditions. Migration (Latin migration - migration, relocation) refers to the movement of a citizen, family or community from one place to another, it is based on the principle of freedom and voluntariness. The process of population migration from one place to another is of a permanent and seasonal nature and can take place within one country and through migration from one country to another. The concept of "resettlement" is based on decisions made by public authorities and other legal norms of a certain part of the population. In it, the displaced population is seen as a driving force and complement to certain methods and relations of production, one of the main reasons for which is to maintain the balance of productive forces and efficient use of labor resources through the territorial redistribution of previously spontaneously located labor and labor resources.

The Resolution of the Council of Ministers of the Uzbek SSR and the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Uzbekistan (b) of April 15, 1949 "On measures for further development of Mirzachul lands" paid special attention to the issue of providing labor force and qualified specialists to newly established farms. To this end, more people from the mountainous and non-cotton-growing regions of the country are involved. In particular, in 1948, 250 farms were relocated from Parkent district of Tashkent region to Mirzachul and Boka districts.[3]. Advocacy work has also begun to bear fruit. For example, a group of people from the village of Bakhmal in the Samarkand region were the first to move to the Boyovut state farm in the Syrdarya region. They were called "KiyikTepa", "Kanop", "DarvozaKir", "Kazak Ovul" due to the structure of the sovkhos lands, arable lands, location of the population and other features. The number of migrants from Samarkand, Tashkent, Fergana and other regions has increased. They leveled Kiyiktepa and planted cotton and orchards in its place. In 1952, the current Boyovut 2 state farm was established. Five years later, the number of people who moved to the state farm from the provinces reached 2,000. In those years, the farm was headed by

UsmonYusupov.[4]. That is why the name of the place of migration is still preserved in the settlements established in Mirzachul. For example, Andijansovkhoz, Samarkand, Forishlikmahalla and others.

From the end of 1953, N.S., who was the first secretary of the Central Committee of the CPSU and at the same time the chairman of the Council of Ministers of the USSR, pursued a voluntarist policy without regard to objective political and economic laws. Khrushchev gave the following instructions on the implementation of the development of protected and gray lands: the development of protected lands is a vital task. Further development of new lands and their introduction into state circulation will bring great economic benefits. But it is not the most difficult to cultivate the land, it is necessary to increase the population, so that the protected lands can be developed.[5]. It can be seen that no matter what the situation, population growth in new lands has always been in the focus of the state.

In the process of implementing the resettlement policy, the government has also begun to take measures to help the population change their previously adapted lifestyle and work in accordance with the established procedure, to get used to living in harmony with the community. In particular, families who moved to the newly developed lands of Uzbekistan and worked on collective and state farms were exempted from agricultural taxes for up to five years. Due to these and similar benefits, the number of families moving to newly developed lands has increased, and in 1966 alone, about 37,000 families in our country moved to protected and gray lands.[6]. So we can see that material incentives have also been more effective in relocating the population.

In 1947, 1863 families moved to the newly established cotton and grain state farms of Uzbekistan, and from 1950 to 1952 3986 families moved. However, the pace of housing construction and staffing in these newly developed areas was far behind demand.[7].

Research materials show that in the post-war years, the workers and employees of the newly formed state farms faced great difficulties in providing them with housing. First of all, due to the fact that the resettlement was not carried out according to the plan, the number of migrants was several times higher than the number of newly built houses. The prolongation of housing construction was caused by regular interruptions in the supply of building materials. In addition, hastily built houses were in urgent need of repair. "In 1950, only 43% of state farm workers were provided with housing" [8]. Workers on many state farms were forced to live in basements or tents due to lack of housing.

Those who moved to the newly acquired lands with great hopes worked hard. As a result, the state not only covered many expenses related to the protection and development of gray lands, but also brought to the state a net income of 18 billion soums. In addition, in 1949-53, an average of 300 billion soums, and in 1954-58 - 400 bln. soums worth of agricultural products were produced.[9].

A scientific study of the resettlement of the population to Mirzachul, measures taken to improve their socio-economic and spiritual-cultural life showed that this policy is a phenomenon that has significantly changed the socio-economic life of the rural population, affecting not only the geographical location of the population national composition and social and demographic changes of the population. The development of the Mirzachul, Karshi, Surkhan-Sherabad, Central Fergana and Jizzakh deserts and the introduction of new lands into agricultural consumption was largely due to the selfless work of the resettled people.

In conclusion, it should be noted that although the resettlement to Mirzachul was widespread, it was not always planned. First of all, during the special internal resettlement policy pursued by the Center in Uzbekistan, the necessary conditions were not created for our compatriots to get used to living away from their place of residence, place of umbilical cord blood and relatives for hundreds of years. First, the pace of construction of housing and socio-economic, cultural and household facilities has lagged behind the pace of development of new lands; second, the hastily commissioned housing was not large enough to accommodate and accommodate the relocating families; thirdly, such houses, built without taking into account the desert conditions and the mentality of the local population, did not meet their requirements and needs, causing many difficulties; fourth, the regular registration and registration of the resettled population by village councils and farm personnel departments was not organized at the required level. In addition, these issues have been postponed due to the fact that the newly resettled population is not well aware of the ways in which they can benefit from the benefits provided to them. As a result, some of the migrants returned to their homelands. it must be said that the specialist cadres, who had migrated without knowing the conditions of the newly acquired territories, believing in various promises, had led to a growing spirit of distrust of the state and the party in the cadres. It is not difficult to understand the socio-economic, cultural and educational life of the people living in the desert, compared with the work done during the study period to provide housing for the population who moved to Mirzachul to develop the country under the "Prosperous Village" program.

References:

1. ЎзРМДА, 314 – фонд, 1 – рўйхат, 415 – йиғма жилд, 10 – варақ.
2. Мирзиёев Ш. Буюк келажагимизни мард ва олий жаноб халқимиз билан бирга қураимиз. – Тошкент: Ўзбекистон, 2017. – 343 бет.
3. Одилхонов О. Паркент. – Тошкент, 1989. – 46 бет.
4. Убайдуллаев О. Мукофот чорлайди. //Меҳнат ва турмуш, 1971, №12. 4-бет.
5. Хрущев Н.С. Қишлоқ хўжалигини янада юксалтириш учун резервлардан тўлароқ фойдаланайлик. Совет Иттифоқи Коммунистик партияси Марказий Комитетининг 1959 йил Декабрь пленумида сўзлаган нутқи, – Тошкент, 1960. – 37 бет.
6. Муллажонов И.Р. Ўзбекистон аҳолисининг миграцион алоқалари. – Тошкент, 1967. – 6 бет.
7. Турсунов С. Қишлоқ аҳолисини уй-жой ва маиший шароитларини яхшилаш муаммолари. – Тошкент, 1994. – 13 бет.
8. Ўша муаллиф. – 10 бет.
9. Қориев М. Ишчи ва деҳқонлар иттифоқи – совет давлати қудратининг асоси. Юридик фан. номзоди дисс. – Тошкент, 1960. – 88 бет.

